

Uses of non-pressure membranes for microalgae biomass harvesting

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ABSTRACT

Harvesting of microalgae biomass is a major challenge in the development of industrial processes related to the management of this type of microorganism. Thus, microalgae are small cells (<10 µm) produced in diluted cultures (<3 g/L) in large volumes of water (>1000 m³/reactor), thus the separation of biomass from the culture broth represents up to 30% of operating costs (Acien et al., 2017). The conventional technology for microalgae harvesting includes the direct centrifugation of the culture or a combination of pre-concentration + dewatering using sedimentation or dissolved air flotation before centrifugation. However, none of these technologies allows for to complete removal of the microalgae cells from the culture broth. The microalgae cells remaining after separation of the biomass make it difficult for the safe disposal of this water or its reuse. The recent development of non-pressure membranes used for membrane bioreactors allows to development of more sustainable processes for the harvesting of microalgae biomass in large-scale processes.

In the present study, the operation of non-pressure membranes for the pre-concentration of microalgae cultures is presented. An experimental setup was designed for this purpose. The operation of the system was firstly optimized, thus the filtration time and frequency of back-wash to achieve stable operation of the membrane was determined. Next, the influence of operational conditions (pressure, biomass concentration) on the performance of the system (flow, specific filtration capacity) was evaluated. Based on these results a model capable of predicting the performance of the process is developed. The feasibility of the developed technology has been validated in large-scale raceway reactors (up to 600 m²) operating in continuous mode. Moreover, the performance of the technology when applying it for the recovery of different microalgae strains was also validated, including for the recovery of biomass from wastewater treatment. Results confirm the reliability and robustness of the technology, representing a relevant improvement contributing to the enlargement of microalgae production systems especially for medium and low-value applications.

KEYWORDS

microalgae, non-pressure membranes, harvesting, pre-concentration, water recycling

REFERENCES

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SPEAKER INFORMATION

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BIOGRAPHY

Graduated from the University of Granada in 1992, and PhD at the University of Almería (Spain) in 1996. Professor at the Department of Chemical Engineering of the University of Almería from 2012 onwards. Prof. Acién has participated in 17 European projects in addition to 45 National projects and contracts with companies. Regarding publications, he published more than 250 papers in international journals and 15 book chapters, in addition to 15 patents. He is Vice-President of EABA and a member of international societies such as the International Society for Applied Phycology, the Latino-American Society for Algal and Environmental Biotechnology, and the Spanish Platform of Biomass (BIOPLAT). He is an editor of Algal Research and RELABIAA journals, in addition to a reviewer of international journals. Major contributions to the Biotechnology of the microalgae field are related to the improvement of photobioreactor design, scale-up of production systems, and economic analysis of production processes. (orcid.org/0000-0002-8434-0365, Scopus ID: 55385950700).

ORGANIZATION PROFILE

The University of Almeria is a public entity focused in education and research. The group from the University of Almería has experience in several aspects of microalgal biotechnology, and during the last years applied this experience to the development of industrial processes based on microalgae. This group participated in different EU projects (i.e. MANTA, ALGINET, EPALMAR, AQUAFUELS, ENERBIOALGAE, CO2ALGAEFIX, MANAGER, SABANA, PRODIGIO), currently participating in up to three new EU projects (REALM, NIAGARA, COSEC), in addition to collaborating with a large number of research centres and universities as well as companies in Europe and worldwide. This group has developed several patents about the design and operation of photobioreactors to produce microalgae, including modelling and advanced control systems. Installations available at the University of Almería include outdoor photobioreactors from 1 to 120 m³ fully instrumented, in addition to reactors at pilot scale for downstream processing from 2 to 300 L and auxiliary equipment. This group combines chemical engineering knowledge with extensive experience in different fields for the scale-up and demonstration of microalgae-based processes.